

COcyber Cybersphere Insights – July 2025

As we move into the second year of [COcyber](#), the project is taking shape across multiple fronts: from **ambassador engagement and national case studies** to digital tools and cross-sector collaboration. This edition shares **highlights from our third General Assembly**, introduces the new cohort of COcyber Ambassadors, and presents two newly released deliverables alongside the latest platform features. It also includes video recaps from our key events, upcoming opportunities from our network, and important developments shaping Europe's cybersecurity strategy.

COCYBER UPDATES

[Meet the Second Batch of COcyber Ambassadors](#)

The COcyber Ambassador Programme enters its second phase with **a new cohort of seven professionals from Belgium, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, and Romania**. Their backgrounds span public policy, operational resilience, capacity building, and cybersecurity innovation. They will support knowledge exchange, amplify the project's visibility, and help bridge civil-military cybersecurity divides.

Welcome onboard: [Dr Vilius Benetis](#), [Iva Tasheva](#), [Gabriella Biró](#), [Csaba Krasznyay](#), [Līga Raita Rozentāle](#), [Yugo Neumorni](#), [Uzoma Agba](#)

[Learn more](#)

[COcyber's First Year: From Vision to Milestones](#)

One year into the project, **COcyber has evolved from concept to a connected community.** Project partners reflected on milestones including the launch of the COcyber platform, the AI Cybersecurity Deephack, and the Ambassador Programme. In a new anniversary video, they share what has made this journey meaningful and what lies ahead in year two.

[▶ COcyber's First Year: Milestones, Meaning, and What Comes Next](#)

[COcyber gathered partners and Advisory Board to its 3rd General Assembly](#)

The third COcyber General Assembly took place in Brussels on 23 - 24 June 2025, bringing together partners and Advisory Board members. Topics discussed during the meeting included **updates from the COcyber Secretariat, a preview of the upcoming platform release and key insights from the recent public consultation on dual-use cybersecurity.**

The agenda also covered communication and dissemination activities, as well as planning for sustainability and exploitation. A hybrid Advisory Board meeting was held, where external experts provided valuable feedback to support the project's next steps.

[Learn more](#)

DELIVERABLES AND TOOLS

[Deliverable 4.3 – Toolkit for the organisation of know-how and information-sharing activities](#)

Led by The Lisbon Council, this **COcyber Project Toolkit** presents a **comprehensive framework for enhancing European civilian-defence cybersecurity collaboration**. It addresses eight critical community needs, including fragmented cybersecurity efforts, uncoordinated policies, limited cross-sector collaboration, and skills shortages. The document outlines six activity types, each strategically aligned with specific community needs and stakeholder groups.

[Check the full toolkit](#)

[Deliverable 6.1 – Interim report on synergies with relevant cybersecurity initiatives and projects](#)

This newly published deliverable, coordinated by AMETIC, identifies 20 high-potential EU-funded projects with relevance to COcyber's mission. The report **maps synergies across five thematic clusters – dual-use technology development, cyber resilience, regulatory alignment, knowledge transfer, and stakeholder engagement** – and outlines opportunities for joint action. These insights will inform the upcoming COcyber Concertation Workshop, planned for September 2025.

[Read the report](#)

Platform Update – New tools for cyber resilience

The COcyber platform has been enhanced with three new features to support informed action and collaboration:

- **COcyber Map:** a visual overview of the European cybersecurity ecosystem, consolidating insights on funding, skills, and national strategies
- **Knowledge Base:** a curated repository of publications and expert resources
- **Policy Coach:** an AI-powered assistant offering practical recommendations for cybersecurity policy development

These additions are designed to support stakeholders working across civilian and defence domains with actionable insights and practical tools.

Welcome to the COcyber Platform, the central digital space of the COcyber project, designed to support and strengthen collaboration between cybersecurity actors across the civilian and defence spheres. This platform brings together a wide range of information, project resources, and other relevant materials in a single, accessible location.

At its core, the platform fosters enhanced coordination and cooperation by providing structured and user-friendly access to essential project outputs and insights. By centralising content and fostering dialogue, the COcyber Platform plays a vital role in achieving the project's vision: to build a sustainable community that spans cybersecurity domains and supports Europe's resilience in the digital age.

COcyber Map

The COcyber Map is an interactive online platform that offers a dynamic visual overview of the EU cybersecurity landscape. It consolidates diverse cybersecurity intelligence—from procurement trends and funding patterns to digital skills and project data—into a single, accessible tool.

Knowledge Base

The COcyber Knowledge Base is a comprehensive and curated repository of documents, designed to support a deeper understanding of the many dimensions and complexities of cybersecurity.

Policy Coach

Coming soon

The COcyber Policy Coach is an innovative AI-powered assistant designed to support policymakers in developing and refining cybersecurity strategies. Powered by generative AI like, the Policy Coach provides actionable insights rooted in best practices and expert knowledge.

[Visit our platform](#)

VIDEO RECAPS

COcyber Ambassador Programme – Batch #1 Recap

Launched in January, the first cohort of COcyber Ambassadors contributed to **community building and knowledge exchange across Europe**. From mentoring at the AI Cybersecurity Deephack to supporting stakeholder engagement and best practice validation, their role has been pivotal in promoting cross-sector dialogue.

 [Meet COcyber Ambassadors Batch 1](#)

AI Cybersecurity Deephack – Highlights from the Challenge

Held in April, the Deephack brought together interdisciplinary teams to tackle phishing threats through dual-use AI innovation. Winning solutions included real-time anomaly detection for autonomous systems, federated learning engines, and graph-based threat detection. The video recap captures the fast-paced intensity, collaborative spirit, and technical ingenuity of the event.

[▶ COcyber AI Cybersecurity Deephack- Recap Video](#)

OPPORTUNITIES FROM OUR NETWORK

[Cybersecurity Essentials Course](#) – EIT Digital Professional School

COcyber platform users can now access a 50% discount for this five-week live training series, organised by EIT Digital in partnership with Women4Cyber Spain. Covering critical cybersecurity topics such as **threat mitigation, device protection, and industry-specific risks**, the course is designed for both individuals and organisations seeking practical, up-to-date defences. Sessions begin on 17 September 2025.

👉 Registered members of COcyber Community can request the discount code by emailing us at contact@cocyber.eu.

[Register to the COcyber Community here](#)

Evolve DualTech – Bridging Civil and Security Innovation

Hosted by Verhaert Strategic Innovation, **Evolve DualTech** supports researchers **working on deep tech with dual-use potential**, technologies that can serve both civilian and defence applications.

The programme combines seven weeks of online training and mentoring with a three-day in-person bootcamp in Brussels. Participants will explore **dual-use strategy and global imperatives**, develop and validate concepts, define prototypes, address IP and compliance, design business models, and build investor-ready pitches and partnerships.

Applications are open until 15 September 2025. **Participation is fully funded, and accommodation during the bootcamp is included.**

Info & registration

NEWS FROM THE FIELD

[Europe's Future Budget Puts Cybersecurity on the Strategic Map](#)

The European Commission has unveiled its proposal for the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) 2028–2034, a nearly €2 trillion investment plan to shape a stronger, more resilient, and secure Europe.

Within the newly proposed European Competitiveness Fund, which dedicates €131 billion to defence, security and space, the Commission highlights that “the military mobility dualuse infrastructure investments that will “contribute to a major boost for cybersecurity, infrastructure, and defence development overall.”

[Find out more](#)

[ENISA Annual Activity Report 2024 Released](#) The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) has published its latest annual report, highlighting **activities related to NIS2, certification frameworks, operational support, and training**. ENISA's growing policy role and cross-sector engagement continue to shape the EU's cyber resilience agenda.

[Full report](#)

⚡ Don't miss any future COcyber events connecting the dots between civilian and defence cyber security initiatives. Join our community now at <https://cocyber.eu/user/register>

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre. Neither can be held responsible for them.